

Category	Label	Description
Demographic info: Document type		
	Experience studies	Documents reporting how something has been used in practice.
	Opinion study	Documents expressing a personal opinion of the author(s) (good or bad aspects) or how they consider things should be done.
	Solution proposal	Documents proposing a new solution using examples or descriptions to argue its effectiveness.
	Validation research	Documents present initial empirical evidence regarding the solution's effectiveness.
Level 1 - Theme: Contribution type		
	Insights from practice	Contributes with support for code review using generative AI technology.
	New solution	Contributes sharing perceptions and insights from experience with generative AI-based tools in code review practice.
Level 2 - Theme: Contribution type - New Solution: Type		
	Review assistant	Document contributes with a new solution that can assist practitioners in code reviews.
	Reviewer bot	Document contributes with a new solution that is an automated approach for performing code review tasks as part of the workflow.
Level 2 - Theme: Contribution type - New Solution: Presentation Type		
	Project Repository	The document is the repository of a software project that uses generative AI to support the code review practice. Often a GitHub repository.
	Proposal Insights	The document presents insights or ideas for a new application to be built using generative AI to support code review practice. It differs from the Tool Presentation by presenting ideas and not an already developed tool.
	Tool Presentation	The document presents a developed tool using generative AI (with or without other technologies) to support the practice of code review. Excludes documents about popular commercial tools such as ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot. It differs from the Proposal Description by presenting an existing approach (not only ideas) and from the Project Repository by not being a source files repository.
Level 2 - Theme: Contribution type - New Solution: Technology Type		
	Browser Extension	The generative AI technology is part of a web browser extension that can review Git requests.
	Plugin IDE	The generative AI technology is part of a plugin for the integrated development environment (IDE) that can review the code within the IDE.
	Plugin ChatGPT	The generative AI technology is part of a plugin for ChatGPT.
	Script	The generative AI technology is part of a script.
	GitHub Action	The generative AI technology is used in the workflow of GitHub Action as a bot, automatically running according to predefined instructions.
	Other	The generative AI technology is part of a specific technology type not covered by existing options.
Level 1 - Theme: Tasks		
Preparation of the review request	Review Request Description	As part of code review, generative AI technology can support better writing of the descriptions often attached to code changes submitted to the code review process.
	Self-code Review	Developers have the support of tools based on generative AI to review their own code changes before submitting them to the code review process.
Reviewers checking and feedback	Code Change Summarization	As part of code review, the generative AI technology can facilitate change summarization to help understand and identify coding issues.
	Review Feedback Provision	The generative AI technology can provide review feedback as part of the code review. This code includes cases in which the generation of review feedback is mentioned, but it is not specified whether it identifies coding issues or provides actionable fix suggestions.

Category	Label	Description
Addressing the review feedback	Coding Issues Explanation	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can provide explanations about a coding issue in a specific change to help the developer understand it.
	Code Fix Execution Support	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can support the developer in performing a code fix, repair, or code improvement suggested by the tool itself or human reviewers.
Level 1 - Theme: Adoption Considerations		
Level 2 - Theme: Adoption Considerations - Benefits		
	Better Code Comprehension	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can support a better code comprehension on the code changes.
	Early First Feedback	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can provide faster first feedback on the code changes.
	Better cost-benefit	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can reduce the process's overall duration, increasing the practice's efficiency.
	Fairly and Thoroughly Feedback	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can provide review feedback comments that are fair and objective.
	Increase Quality	As part of the code review, the generative AI technology can support an increase of code and/or product quality.
	Learning Support	As part of the code review, generative AI technology can help practitioners learn about coding and best practices.
	Sparks Collaborative Discussions	Adopting tools based on generative AI can promote collaborative discussions during the code review process.
Level 2 - Theme: Adoption Considerations - Challenges		
	Generative AI Trustworthiness	Determining whether generative AI models and platforms can be trusted without human intervention is challenging, including the difficulty related to model bias and its often "black box" structure.
	Misleading Review Comments	It is a challenge to rely on code review comments provided by generative AI models, given the misleading or poor quality examples sometimes observed.
	Lack of Context	It is a challenge to rely on suggestions from generative AI models, given their limitations in understanding the context.
	Security and Privacy	It is challenging to ensure the confidentiality of private code and compliance with security and privacy policies when using generative AI technologies.
	Token Limit	Given the current token limit, it is a challenge to provide large amounts of data for some generative AI-based tools. In the case of code review, processing significant code review changes is difficult due to this limitation.